

raisd

Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

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Research stories from ARUs: Report and Analysis

Deliverable D7.1

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

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Document Information

Grant Agreement #:	822688
Project Title:	Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced
Project Acronym:	RAISD
Project Start Date:	1 st February, 2019
Related work package:	WP7 Cross analysis
Deliverable:	D7.1 Research stories from ARUs: report and analysis
Related task(s):	T7.1 Integrating ARU research stories
Lead Organisation:	UNIMED Mediterranean Universities Union
Submission date:	29/10/2021 (Month 33)
Dissemination Level:	Public

History

Date	Submitted by	Reviewed by	Version (Notes)
29/10/2021	UNIMED	All Partners	Version 1

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<i>About RAISD</i>	
<i>Call (part) identifier</i>	<i>H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018</i>
<i>Topic</i>	<i>MIGRATION-08-2018 Addressing the challenge of forced displacement</i>
<i>Fixed EC Keywords</i>	<i>Globalisation, migration, interethnic relations</i>
<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

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Executive Summary

The main goal of this deliverable is to collect relevant information and witnesses about the co-creation process which led the RAISD project partners to set up the Action Research Units (known as ARUs) and to implement the Tailored Attention Inclusion Strategies (in short, TAIS): on the basis of the collected information, some conclusions were drawn about the main challenges faced by the partners, including both the successful and the improvable aspects of the project.

In order to do that, the UNIMED team, leading the corresponding task of the workplan, collected and analysed information from various sources: in the first place, the team went through the many deliverables produced by the partners reporting on the activities they performed in the first two years of the project's lifetime, and then a set of interviews were carried out at two levels:

- At the partnership level, the UNIMED team interviewed the ARU leaders, to understand the main challenges they faced and to plan the second level of interviews;
- At the ARUs level, external stakeholders participating in the ARUs different from the project partners, as well as some final beneficiaries were interviewed to collect external views about the work of the ARUs and the impact of the TAIS.

Of course the project was very hardly hit by the COVID 19 pandemic which completely jeopardised the timing of the activities and in some cases even their feasibility, and the way in which the ARUs reacted to this unforeseen event and showed resilience was one of the important issues at stake in the information collection process.

On this basis the Deliverable D7.1 is structured as follows:

- In the introductory sections of the document, some background information about the project as such, the organisation of work and the way the work has been carried out is provided;
- Then the goals of the deliverable and the methodology adopted to fulfil these goals (such as, inter alia, the two-level interview structure) a presented;
- The bulk of the document is then represented by seven sections, one for each ARU, where the ARU stories are told, and links are provided to the video recording of some of the interviews. Due to the severe privacy and personal security regulations and RAISD measures for protecting forcibly displaced people, some of the persons involved could not have their identities made public and therefore not all the interviews could be video recorded. In these cases, an anonymised transcription was provided. Otherwise, an informed consent was obtained.
- In the last paragraph some conclusions are drawn, essentially focussing on:
 - The many difficulties of **involving and keeping the levels of engagement of the stakeholders** (problems in finding the right motivation, avoiding withdrawal) and **the final beneficiaries** (providing them with added value when participating in the activities);
 - The **impact of the pandemic and how the ARUs reacted to that**, especially considering that, dealing with vulnerable groups, turning the activities into online events was not always a viable option;
 - And finally, some considerations on the **overall achievements of the ARU and on their innovation contents**.

1 Overview of the RAISD Project

The RAISD project aims at identifying vulnerable groups among forcibly displaced people, their specific challenges and needs, to provide them tailored attention and inclusion strategies. Main objectives:

- Discover highly vulnerable groups among Forcibly Displaced People.
- Develop the novel concept of vulnerability context to gain a different perspective in dealing with migration.
- Analyse their specific challenges and needs regarding integration and well-being.
- Identify suitable and evidence-based aid strategies to promote their involvement and improve their inclusion in host societies.

Research strategies:

- Combine methodological triangulation of Responsible Research and Innovation, action research, and socio-ecological models.
- Monitor inclusion measures for vulnerable migrants developing innovative standard methods (Collaborative Research and Innovation Online tool).
- Co-design actions transversely integrating the gender perspective and supporting sustainability.
- Integration of Social and Computer Sciences research.

Innovative Results:

- Vulnerability Contexts. The treatment of phenomena related to VGs in FDPs requires understanding the context where they happen. This context involves three components. First, the people of the VG, with their vital trajectories, contexts of departure, and individual vicissitudes. Second, the host environments and their societies, with their history, culture, socio-economic situation, civil society, and attitudes towards FDP and VGs. Third, the interactions between the previous two elements.
- TAIS - Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies. Strategies are innovative as they define effective practices (i.e. highly scored by criteria) for a given context describing the correspondence between Vulnerability Contexts, implemented practices and criteria for their evaluation. Just as an example, In terms of, e.g., target group, objectives, requirements, type of host community, actual results, related artefacts and evaluation by actors.
- CRIOS - Collaborative Research and Innovation Online Software tool. The state-of-the-art platform integrates functionalities for information and knowledge sharing by different actors involved in the research project, and the related analysis tools that will be fully free/open source software and use open standards and protocols to facilitate interoperability.
- Ensure the adoption of innovative policies and practices to address new challenges in the field of migration.

2 Objectives of the ARU

The Action Research Units (ARUs) are multidisciplinary groups set up in each partner city and distributed throughout Central-Eastern (Hungary), Southern (Spain and Italy) and Northern (Finland) parts of Europe, as well as Asia (Turkey) and Middle East (Jordan, Lebanon). The locally based Units collaborate with local organisations to explore the potential conflict and intrinsic difficulties of addressing both the local demands of society on the issues of FDP inclusion, and the local and global demands to contribute to a more equitable and sustainable society. Each single ARU covers a territorial scope related with the country of establishment (e.g. Finland's ARU has the Finnish territory as geographical scope). The ARUs have a national scope and are focused on national vulnerability contexts and groups. Moreover, the ARUs have:

1. Contributed to the research design providing feedback;
2. Contributed to the data collection;
3. Selection, adaptation, implementation and evaluation of TAISs;
4. Defined Roadmap for TAISs definition and implementation;
5. Set up and test the TAISs for their VCs and provide relevant feedback.

2.1 Roles and Responsibilities of stakeholders taking part in an ARU

The ARUs are responsible for gathering information that characterise the vulnerable groups and their lives, as well as related institutions and societal actors. Moreover, the ARUs are also responsible for the co-creation of research activities where all relevant stakeholders play an active role in the definition, execution and evaluation (RRI approach); setting-up, piloting and testing of the TAISs 'Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies' for each specific Vulnerability Context and provide the relevant feedback; undertake advocacy-focused participatory action-research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. Moreover, the stakeholders taking part in the ARUs are responsible for:

- Identifying reports and key literature sources for the research unit.
- Taking part in the information production process: interviews, participatory workshops and focus groups.
- Assisting in fieldwork (contacts and advice on proceedings).
- Reading, revising and commenting on the key documents created by RAISD.
- Giving relevant feedback on the project development.
- Assisting to test (and when possible, hosting) the Tailored Action and Inclusion Strategies.

2.2 Structure and Organization of the ARUs

ARUs have been set up as multidisciplinary groups with representatives from all types of stakeholders. Indicatively, between 10 (minimum) and 15 (maximum) stakeholders' representatives have been involved into each ARU, many more when possible (such is the case of CESIE and UCM). In other cases, such as for LIU or Menedék, fewer stable actors form the ARU, while many other stakeholders have been consulted on an occasional basis and in case of specific need. The criterion of the quintuple helix was taken into account in setting up the ARU. Thus, the objective to have at least one representative of each helix has been achieved, but in Finland for two reasons mainly: lack of

connections with the private sector and closed nature of the Finnish reception system dominated by officials and NGOs.

In order to avoid fragmentation and a too wide differences in the composition of the ARUs, we considered it fundamental to give an indication to partners also to harmonize different ARUs in terms of participation and dimensions, and indications have been followed.

2.3 TAIS Implementation

Partners in the project have worked developing Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAIS) which define effective practices (i.e. highly scored by stakeholder criteria) for a given vulnerability context (as defined by field research – to know more you can consult D.4.2 about VCs). Each TAIS in each of the seven involved countries has been implemented through a cycle of three successive pilots (between April 2020 and October 2021), each pilot being evaluated in order to provide feedback to the research dimension of the project, and adapting the next pilot round on the basis of this evaluation in order to make the TAIS more and more effective. Piloting and evaluation took place with the full involvement of the final beneficiaries (FDPs) as well as working with stakeholders in the framework of the Action Research Units (ARUs).

The TAIS in each country is designed by the respective RAISD consortium member institution and the ARUs. Their work is coordinated by three project members. Methodology issues are supervised by the project's lead partner, the Complutense University of Madrid. The implementation is coordinated by Menedék – Hungarian Association for Migrants. The evaluation is carried out by the University of Helsinki. On the other hand, the work of the ARU, their involvement in the action, their engagement routine and contribution are monitored by UNIMED.

3 Scope and goals of Deliverable 7.1: “Research stories from ARUs: report and analysis”

This definition is taken from the Description of Action:

D7.1 is the output of Task 7.1 which leads the sharing of case research stories from the Action Research Units (ARUs) in the project partner countries, and it further explores their intersections. These reports from the field enable a deeper understanding of Tailored Attention and Inclusion Practices (TAISs), their related problems, barriers and enablers, as well as their dependencies with contextual factors (e.g. cultural, political, normative and legal). Building up these research stories is a co-creation process itself, as the stakeholders are given an active voice in what is presented and how it is presented. Key elements of these stories are those related to the project results, but also reflective dimensions about their context (inclusion, anticipation, transparency and responsiveness). Research stories include traditional reports from stakeholders using templates, but also multimedia productions of interviews with stakeholders and on-site documentations of the co-creation processes.

In order to fulfil this objective, we have collected information in several forms, documenting the ways the ARUs have been working (most of which was contained in previous deliverables), collecting live interventions from a sample of the involved actors, and asking the ARU leaders to provide feedbacks on the setting up and functioning of the ARUs and their TAIS by engaging stakeholders other than the project Partners. The key is a change of perspective, stories

are told by the people directly involved, such as members of the ARUs and/or beneficiaries of the TAIS. The idea is to collect witnesses of the ARUs work and/or impact of the TAIS. Stakeholders have been asked to describe the ARU and the TAIS in which they have been involved.

It must be noted here that it has been virtually impossible to decouple the aspects of TAIS implementation from those related to the process of setting up and implementing the ARUs: in fact, the TAISs are the main and most relevant output of the ARUs and their *raison d'être*, therefore it would have made little sense to focus exclusively on the ARUs without analysing the TAIS.

3.1 Roadmap for implementation – Methodology of work to collect the ARU stories

In the frame of the above definition, the contents of this deliverable have been collected according to the following methodology.

In the first place, the reports on the implementation of ARUs and TAIS have been analysed to understand the background on which to develop the contents of D7.1 and to avoid duplication. Under this respect, the deliverables produced by WP5 and the informal reports on the implementation of the TAIS have been taken into account.

Secondly, the ARU leaders were asked to compile a short report, based on a template which was circulated to this purpose, highlighting a number of key aspects of the ARUs work and of TAIS implementation, the main ones being:

- Stakeholders' engagement;
- Impact of the cultural, political, and legal context;
- Positive and innovative factors;
- Transfer of knowledge of great value to stakeholders;
- Other initiatives, different to the TAIS, having emerged as a result of the ARU's activity;
- Future perspectives for the work of ARUs, sustainability.

Thirdly, the ARU leaders have been asked to interview either a representative of the stakeholders participating in the ARU other than the RAISD project partner, or a final beneficiary of the TAIS or both. Concerning the format of the interview, ARUs have been invited on a voluntary basis to choose between the following options:

- record a short video / interview
- send a written testimony
- send a picture of the experience with a brief description
- take part in an interview with UNIMED (via Zoom)

As a guide to the ARU members and beneficiaries, a set of possible topics for the interview were proposed:

- Difficulties encountered in implementing the TAIS
- Success achieved / Factors of success
- How have you been involved in the work of the ARU / in the TAIS
- Innovative factors of your experience
- Impact on your professional experience

- Transferability of ARU / TAIS experience in other contexts/working activities
- Future perspectives

All the resulting research stories are presented in this deliverable with a storytelling approach, and these are also being made available on the project website (<https://raisd-h2020.eu/research/aru/>). The current document also includes a brief description of the ARU composition and the TAIS implemented, as a set of background information for the testimonies. Due to privacy and confidentiality concerns and to protect FDP's anonymity and prevent traceability, particularly significant in the context of some of the ARUs, in some cases the identity of the participants has not been disclosed.

3.2 *The testimonials*

Upon the availability of stakeholders, the ethics requirements of the project and taking into consideration the specificities of each national context, UNIMED asked the ARU leaders to collect contributions ideally from:

- A member of the ARU which is not a project Partner
- A direct beneficiary of the TAIS implemented

In the case of the above not being available to tell the ARU stories, other stakeholders from the ARU itself have been involved and interviewed. In most cases, they have been asked to narrate also the experience of the final beneficiaries of the TAIS, therefore widening the perspective of the stories.

All testimonials and testimony provided in the framework of the research work, and therefore reported in the current document, do not constitute any risk for those involved. The data is provided after receiving an informed consent of the participants and no risk or harm can be infringed to those accepting to appear or be named.

4 ARU in Spain – the work of Universidad Complutense de Madrid (UCM)

4.1 Background information

The Spanish ARU was set at the Universidad Complutense de Madrid, using the facilities offered by the university itself. The UCM team counted on several experts in Social and Computer Sciences, with a background in RRI and forced migration to start the work of the ARU. UCM team was able to leverage on previous experience in projects and innovation actions to activate contacts and participants. The first ARU meeting took place in July 2019. Later, with the COVID-19 outbreak, the meetings were all held online. Both in face to face and virtual ARU meetings, all attendees were divided into working groups to discuss about the different issues that were posed. The ARU started working as an open structure, welcoming experts and actors from different fields due to their interesting profiles, being them experts in dealing with the detected vulnerable group, with forced displaced people, or upon recommendation of other ARU members. The process of engagement of stakeholders was an ongoing process along the years. As an example, some institutions, specialists and civil society activists, for example already working with Sub-Saharan women, were identified later in the project, once that this vulnerable group was chosen for the TAIS. Examples of the ARU actors include UNHCR, Red Cross Spain, and Madrid City Council. The most difficult helixes to involve were companies/business, public administration and individual FDP. In the specific case of the Spanish ARU, it was crucially important to engage beneficiaries of the TAIS, to avoid revictimization. However, especially for the FDP, the change of residence prevented many from joining the ARU meetings with continuity.

As a result of the fieldwork and the discussion in the ARU, one of the vulnerable groups that was identified was Sub-Saharan women because of the special difficulties for inclusion during transit and destination areas: violence, racism, gender discrimination, language, and greater migratory mourning. To these vulnerabilities, being single mothers or family charges can be added. On the other hand, all interviewers during the fieldwork highlighted the difficulty of finding a decent and stable job in Spain.

The aim of this TAIS is to develop skills to promote the socioeconomic inclusion of sub-Saharan refugee women or applicants for international protection in Spain. The women beneficiaries are the principal actors, the centre of the action. All resources are at their disposal. The TAIS focuses on empowering the group of beneficiaries and promoting their autonomy. It is a training and support process with two courses of action:

1. In terms of entrepreneurship, so that they can create a collective productive project (cooperative).
2. Strengthening of abilities and preparation for a greater employability and professional growth.

4.2 Changing the migrants' narratives empowering beneficiaries to start their own businesses

The Spanish ARU has worked since the beginning with high ambitions. Given the capacity of the project, the ARU leaders and members aim to drive an actual change in the lives of the beneficiaries, providing them with tools and advices to face discrimination, empowering them through inclusion, understanding and real-life support. They aim to advise beneficiary women and support their business development. Final beneficiaries are activated through learning and exchange processes, labour insertion and accompaniment dynamics with other women. The work of the ARU became even more relevant and necessary in the current isolation situation due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and the health and social crisis. Moreover, the ARU worked coherently in the promotion of a change in the narratives

of the migrants themselves, knowing that there are different possibilities for their future, involving volunteers, the university and the society in general in the co-creation of new, powerful and meaningful stories. Another great element of strength in the Spanish ARU was the ability to engage stakeholders well beyond the TAIS implementation, producing a change not only in the beneficiaries' lives, but also in the working methodology and approaches of all the organisations involved. In this sense, exchange has been a driving factor and one of the main side-effects of the ARU establishment, enriching in turn the outcomes of the project itself.

The ARU has faced different challenges. How were you able to involve different stakeholders of the helix?

At first, the most difficult helixes to involve were policy makers and business. But, without a doubt, the most difficult helix was business. The Spanish ARU has among the stakeholders some organisations focused on entrepreneurship with migrants, and occupation of migrants. Nevertheless, their availability for the ARU meetings and reports for the TAIS is smaller than other helixes such as NGOs. In the specific case of TAIS beneficiaries, they have not participated in ARU meetings except on rare occasions, as reported by the ARU Leader, such as TAIS evaluations, due to their Spanish level and the difficulty of participating on equal terms with social services providers. Nevertheless, other forced migrants have actively participated in ARU meetings, granting the success and efficacy of the Unit.

How to overcome difficulties in the decision-making process, in the co-creation processes?

A key issue to avoid the problem is anticipation before misunderstandings may arise. ARU members feel free to express their opinion and ideas. A space of free participation has been created, since many stakeholders' needs and complaints are shared. The rise of anti-immigration political parties in Spain has not affected the Third Sector in this regard, except that some experts asked to be identified at an individual level and not representing the official position of their organisations.

How to avoid losing the participation of ARU members that are not directly involved in the TAIS? How to motivate stakeholders to participate in the ARUs work?

A big challenge has been not losing the participation of ARU members that are not directly involved in the TAIS. UCM has worked to do so by different means, such as providing perspective to the work of the ARU in the future. Means of engagement were: talking about the future observatory; using the online platform to share information and good practices related to their expertise; the development of policy recommendations so that necessities can be heard; participation of forced migrants that are not included in the TAIS in the documentary film...

Positive and innovative factors of the ARU working

- We have managed to hold bimonthly meetings, even with the added difficulties of the pandemic. It is an ARU in constant growth, operation, and participation.
- There has been a transfer of knowledge of great value to stakeholders and their organizations, which can be a factor of innovation and generate positive impacts on their professional experience. Methodologies and new forms of participation, project results, good practices, training courses, new contacts, and work networks are some examples of transference.
- Spaces have been created to share experiences among the different stakeholders of the helixes of RRI.

- Other initiatives, different to the TAIS, have emerged as a result of the ARU's activity: teaching innovation activities, contacts for the documentary, an app in collaboration with university students and the knowledge of ARU members, an international conference for young researchers and innovators (Research for Change), a story contest, collecting ideas for the future observatory...

4.3 Testimonials

"It gives me the opportunity to activate and create, from a network that considers different voices: migrants and refugees themselves, social organizations, and the university"

The stakeholder narrating the experience in the framework of the Spanish ARU is Maribel Rodríguez from the organization La Merced Migraciones, a civil society organization which has been working for more than 30 years to guarantee protection and promotion of the inclusion of migrants and refugees in vulnerable situations. The interview is a tangible proof of the willingness of stakeholders to participate in the ARU, despite being oversaturated in their jobs, taking the project as the opportunity to grow, share and be heard. From conversations, dialogue and exchange very valuable people met, with great contributions. The great human capital of the ARU members is rewarded through the ARU work itself. Maribel highlighted how the ARU contributed to her routine both professionally and personally. It gave her the opportunity to stop and think, analyse and exchange impressions; to activate and create, from a network that considers different voices: migrants and refugees themselves, social organizations, and the university; to serve participating women, assess actions and improve. It also helped her to acquire a methodology of work, facilitate and systematize initiatives, planning carefully. Personally, it provided her the opportunity to listen to others' experiences, other ways of doing things, challenging and building her way of being in the world. All in all, it was a valuable learning experience, learning new approaches and visions on vulnerability and vulnerable contexts.

The testimony is available here: <https://youtu.be/YxerDVLPIsg>

5 ARU in Italy – the work of CESIE

5.1 Background information

The Italian ARU is a [Competence Cell](#) which functions under the [Higher Education and Research Unit](#) of CESIE as a knowledge-community at local level offering targeted and tailored services based on the specific needs of stakeholders and related target groups. Considering deeply rooted systemic barriers and the present historical political instability in Italy that might preclude stakeholders' active involvement, RAISD represents a great opportunity for the Italian ARU / the Competence Cell and its impact network to continue the work on migration and specific Vulnerability Contexts. The Cell uses community and bottom-up initiatives, creating a trans-disciplinary network of practitioners to support local infrastructures and contribute to community building, capacity building and awareness raising. Indeed, the Competence Cell takes advantage of a multitude of local partners that contribute to project implementation at different levels, and emerge competences of the staff members of six Units (Higher Education and Research Unit, Right and Justice, Adult, Migration, School and Youth).

The Italian TAIS focuses on forcibly displaced women, and it aims at providing them with online learning tools. The central idea behind the strategy is to personalise online learning through ALL you can LEARN" (AUCL), based on which vulnerable women can have control over their own learning process. The ultimate aim is to increase beneficiaries' decision-making capacity - Forcibly Displaced Women living and/or exposed to highly vulnerable situations and conditions - and to have direct influence over their learning path's contents and modalities according to a set of individual variables (interests and aspirations, level of studies and previously attended programmes, logistics and time availability, etc.) by using online Learning Objectives MENU Tool (Digitalised Admix Selection Interface) infrastructure at <https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/learn>.

5.2 Italian ARU: The Competence Cell, participation and resilience

The strength of the Competence Cell relies on a smooth involvement of stakeholders. The systematic stakeholder involvement process has started already in 2017 (with the H2020 [FoTRRIS project](#) "Fostering a Transition towards Responsible Research and Innovation Systems") and continued within RAISD. As the Competence Cell body was officially established in April 2018, a wide network of stakeholders and target groups were already involved in several local and international activities of CESIE and were naturally engaged in RAISD, letting the working group naturally progress on the implementation of the Action Research Strategy. This has been possible due to the building of trustworthy relationships and successful collaborations that CESIE was able to put in place over many years of cooperation with identified stakeholders. Moreover, a number of stakeholders have been involved in the Italian ARU thanks to their involvement in other CESIE's activities, reinforcing the inclusion mechanism of the network. As an example, external stakeholders involved in the RAISD fieldwork activities have been selected with the support of CESIE's [Migration Unit](#). Also actors of institutional, academic and societal impact are contributing to the work of the Competence Cell, such as psychological and health support services, hosting community and migrants' associations, representatives of civil society.

The ARU has faced different challenges. How were you able to involve different stakeholders of the helix?

As the complexity of the project is very considerable, the ARU satisfies the need for a renowned systemic body that envisions and invests in the growth of significant long-term cooperation relationships and social networks, building a safe community around the highly vulnerable target groups along the inclusion process. The involvement of diverse esteemed experts and practitioners in the action-research model has allowed the accomplishment of quality in the data gathering, also in regards to the various methodologies applied, including analysis levels on vulnerable profiles and contexts, identification of potential Good Practices and contributed to different perspectives as to how to proceed when designing and implementing the TAIS, Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies. The combined actions further improved and expanded the dialogue between institutions, bodies, associations and grassroots who have been working together for years to construct inclusive processes for highly vulnerable groups in the city of Palermo. During the pilot experience itself, important direct and indirect synergies were created at local level with other institutions and centres that support the well-being, education and autonomy of trafficked women. Collaboration was acknowledged by: the centre's psychologist and doctor, the Provincial Centres for Adult Education (CPIA) and Carabinieri (national gendarmerie of Italy who primarily carries out domestic policing duties).

How to overcome difficulties in the decision-making process, in the co-creation processes?

Part of the decision-making process and continuously contributing to the further development and update of the definition of “Vulnerability Contexts” has been CESIE’s INTEGRA Network (committed to sharing experiences, good practices and initiatives to promote paths of accompaniment to autonomy for young and vulnerable Forcibly Displaced). Initial assumptions and considerations regarding contexts that provoke and/or increase vulnerabilities had to be reconsidered in time, especially due to the first, second and third COVID-19 outbreaks in Italy. The Network represented reliable primary source data, gathering multi-stakeholder perspectives on vulnerability as an intersubjective relation and dependent on actors’ viewpoints. Active members of the Network include all quintuple helix stakeholders’ representatives and migrant associations and individuals (currently 34 members from migrant communities/associations, civil society, private social organisations, entrepreneurs and public institutions/local authorities). Reference: <https://cesie.org/en/integra-network/>

How to avoid losing the participation of ARU members that are not directly involved in the TAIS? How to motivate stakeholders to participate in the ARUs work?

Participation of Italian ARU stakeholders was motivated by clear, smart and long-term cooperation objectives:

- To set and sustain a common quality framework for Learning and Training Environments (LTE) tailored for any Highly Vulnerable target groups profile
- To enable quality assurance mechanisms and further improve learning-teaching environments for HVG;
- To monitor and evaluate critical points of implementation cycles;
- To support mutual trust and facilitate recognition and stakeholders’ long-term cooperation, building a safe community around the highly vulnerable target groups along the inclusion process.

Positive and innovative factors of the ARU working

During the first COVID-19 lockdown period, there was a forced increase of distance learning methods and approaches, that found professionals in education unprepared in the delivery modes and knowledge multiplication – therefore, a specific request was to establish also a Resource Database for this secondary target group. The RAISD

Resource Database for professionals in education was created, addressing the need for inclusive learning environments with special attention to distinctively Vulnerable Groups among the Forcibly Displaced and migrant communities in Europe. The learning materials aimed to support creative skills in education for youth, adults, vocational education and training, school communities as well as in Higher Education, providing guidance, training and teaching material with a focus on different methodologies tailored to specific target group segments and contexts of vulnerability. The Italian ARU and Community of Users can register to comment and rate all current 161 educational resources. Registered users can propose new material to be uploaded to the online database. To know more about this innovative approach please consult: <https://allyoucanlearn.cesie.org/teach/>.

5.3 Testimonials

“Your main strength is your capacity to break down the cultural and language barriers”

The first testimony of the Italian ARU comes from Mr. Giuseppe Spinelli, an educator of the Freedom centre, a centre working with trafficked women. CESIE partnered with the “[Cooperativa Nuova Generazione](#), Freedom centre” in the nearby town of Trabia (20 km distance from Palermo) Freedom centre to implement the TAIS, contributing to the integration and inclusion of the vulnerable women arriving to the centre by arranging training sessions with and for them. Point of strength of the Italian ARU has been working on the territory and collaborating with different stakeholders, putting in place a network of operators from different fields to achieve the highest impact on the beneficiaries. Giuseppe highlights in his testimony the great enthusiasm and satisfaction of the young women for the opportunity offered by CESIE, and the participation in the training session was indeed massive. Among the main strengths of the TAIS and the work of the ARU, he noticed the capacity to break down the cultural and language barriers, and the ability of making the training highly interactive, engaging the participating women not only in the learning as such but also involving them emotionally, paying attention to their feelings during the process.

The testimony is available here: <https://youtu.be/D-ALH805j7I>

“Your training was able to answer to their questions, about independence, about work, about the future, and to inspire their curiosity”

The second testimonial of the Italian ARU is Ms. Luigia Sunseri, one of the educators of the Freedom centre. During her interview, she immediately highlighted the importance of having the training delivered directly by CESIE at the centre. That was a key element for the girls hosted in the centre, increasing their feelings of confidence, security, protection and wellbeing. Noteworthy was the great capacity on behalf of the CESIE to involve the young women in the training, raising their curiosity and providing them with support in their path to the future. The hands-on part of the training was essential to match wishes and expectations with actual possibilities and competences. The initiative jointly delivered by CESIE and the Freedom centre was indeed a success for the inclusion and integration of the women, also looking at the long-term perspective it may open for them, towards a new independent space for their own lives. At the very end of her intervention, Luigia stressed the constructive and fruitful collaboration put in place with CESIE, that the centre welcomed very positively, and will be ready to welcome in the future as well.

The testimony is available here: <https://youtu.be/6VD5CRnOQ9g>

“Several optional modules are offered and participants choose contents attractive for them”

Counting on the fundamental support of the mediator and the educators who work in the centres, the first two sessions of the #ALLyoucanLEARN training was delivered to women coming from Somalia and Nigeria. The Italian ARU has relied on a number of figures and actors to make sure the experience of beneficiaries was tailored and of high quality. The networking capacity of the ARU and the trust in the expertise on the field allowed for an effective and efficient working routine on behalf of the members. In turn, it resulted into an impactful TAIS. Participants to the #ALLyoucanLEARN training were easily getting familiar with the training, showing interest in the individualized learning experiences. The novelty of the 'ALL you can LEARN' (AuCL) selective-learning approach has been the introduction of a more bottom-up and participatory practice to education, shifting from an induced training offer to a "selective" approach in developing a training, in which several optional modules are offered and participants can choose contents that are attractive for them. The pictures below narrate from a different point of view the story of the ARU: engagement (both of stakeholders and beneficiaries), impact (on the working cells as well on the vulnerable women), continuity and the crucial importance of valuable interactions.

Figure 1: TAIS implementation, June 2021

6 ARU in Finland – the work of the University of Helsinki

6.1 Background information

As an institution, the University of Helsinki does not have established contacts to the professional fields of so-called frontline workers (contrary to some specialised research institutes in Finland). Therefore, most contacts to potential ARU members have been created from scratch. However, Finland is a small country in terms of population and the public sector is quite centralized. It was thus rather easy to figure out possible members and potential experts for the Finnish ARU.

The core team of the Finnish ARU was established in a meeting in September 2019. ARU members in more local levels have been recruited during spring 2020.

A quite distinct challenge in the process of starting the Finnish ARU was the language issue. The public and third sector experts even on refugee and Forced Displaced People - FDPs - matters tend to be white Finnish-speaking majority not skilled in languages of the FDPs. Consequently, as one of the first steps in setting up the ARU, there was a need to find people who could master Arabic and Dari/Farsi (most common languages among FDPs in Finland), as well as English or Finnish. The solution was to recruit two subcontractors as research assistants. A further challenge in forming the ARU was the multi-sited and two-fold approach of the Finnish sub-project. The aim was to promote two Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies - TAIS - in various reception centres.

In Finland, in fact, the TAIS is designed in the form of two parallel pilot activities that target asylum seekers who are in a vulnerable situation. First, a multilingual online forum for asylum seeking and Finnish-speaking men is piloted with men from several reception centres and with the help of many professionals. Second, childcare activities are developed in the context of two reception centres. Thus, the composition of the Finnish ARU is not fixed while different people are involved in developing, implementing and evaluating different activities.

6.2 Young men and single parents: the Finnish's ARU cases

Overall in Finland, asylum seekers are among the Forced Displaced People (FDPs) in the most vulnerable position. Particularly those who arrived in Finland during 2015-2016 have been forced to live in uncertainty with marginal legal status and with restricted rights for several years. As said, the Finnish ARU focused on asylum seekers. The action was designed in two parallel activities, one targeting young men with no social connections, and the other targeting single parents with small children. Young single asylum-seeking men are rarely seen to be in a vulnerable position. However, these men miss the support of their families, are treated as adults in the asylum process and reception system and are susceptible to discrimination and labour market exploitation and lack targeted services. More specifically, young asylum-seeking men lack the opportunities to use and learn everyday language with Finnish-speaking peers. Most of the contacts they have with Finnish-speakers are elderly women since they tend to volunteer through NGOs. Particularly in smaller towns and rural areas there are few possibilities in contacting Finnish-speaking young people. Moreover, according to several asylum seeker interviews, the language tuition within the reception centres is not enough, takes place only in classrooms and is too repetitive due to constantly changing teachers and learners and the huge diversity of educational backgrounds different asylum seekers have.

The **Multi-lingual online forum** has been a new experiment in the field of Finnish reception centres. It was conceived involving a voluntary group of young asylum-seeking men to join, together with Finnish-speaking voluntary young men in an online thread to discuss the experiences of asylum seekers and everyday life in the Finnish society. The discussions are moderated and, when needed, translated from languages used by asylum seekers into Finnish.

The second activity is about the **development of child-care services in reception centres**. It was aimed to develop already existing services and not to invent new ones. It targets asylum-seeking parents with small children. Parents of small children, particularly single parents, suffer from lack of child-care services while trying to cope in highly stressful conditions. Finnish society provides quite all-encompassing services for families with small children. However, this applies only to families with a residence permit. In most Finnish regions, asylum seeking families do not have the right to early childhood education in municipal day-care centres. Asylum-seeking children are entitled to enter the Finnish education system in pre-school at the age of six. Moreover, the level of child-care services provided varies significantly between different reception centres. Some centres do not organize childcare services at all while, at best, some centres provide help in childcare for a few hours per week. For many families and particularly to single parents, this type of context tends to cause problems or aggravate already existing ones. Children miss structured activities with their peers and their learning and integration to Finnish society are often severely hampered. As for parents, they have difficulties in using the services they are entitled to and their abilities to work or educate themselves and rest are highly limited. Consequently, lack of childcare services has several repercussions on both parental and child wellbeing.

The ARU has faced different challenges. How were you able to involve different stakeholders of the helix?

Actually, we were not able to include all the helixes. This was mostly because:

- lack of connections with the private sector and
- closed nature of the Finnish reception system dominated by officials and NGOs.

How to overcome difficulties in the decision-making process, in the co-creation processes?

This has not been easy because of all the Covid-19 related restrictions. We have had to resort to online discussions in creating trust between various actors. For instance, we have contacted asylum seekers with research interviews, visiting them in reception centres and even their homes when possible and developing various online methods. Despite the efforts, including as many stakeholders as we would have wanted, it has been difficult. Motivating reception centre professionals has been particularly difficult due to recent budget cut downs and reduced number of asylum seekers as a result of closed borders.

How to avoid losing the participation of ARU members that are not directly involved in the TAIS? How to motivate stakeholders to participate in the ARUs work?

The best way to get people motivated is to design things that are considered beneficial. During the Covid era it has been a necessity to contact ARU members on a regular basis and to provide them with up-to-date information about project activities.

Positive and innovative factors of the ARU working

Careful work and knowledge production among asylum seekers has been the key issue in the Finnish sub-project. This has opened up new insights to vulnerabilities of the FDP population and revealed important gaps in the service provision within the reception system in Finland. Consequently, the familiar lesson learned has been the importance of thoroughly involving the so-called end-users in knowledge production and in designing new practices.

6.3 Testimonials

The experience of the Finnish ARU is told from different perspectives. A young asylum seeker coming from Ghana and living in Finland for two years now, the director of the Rovaniemi Reception Centre, a small city in Northern Finland and the assistant manager and a physiotherapist of the Kristiinankaupunki Reception Centre, in Western Finland. Both these two centres are part of the Finnish Red Cross.

“This is what I want to do, to calm people down whenever they join this forum, give them the necessary information and ask them the things that I know the camp is not going to ask them”

Stephen Oppong, a young man from Ghana, has participated in the Finnish ARU, at first as final beneficiary and then as a moderator to help further young men, asylum seekers, who have arrived in Finland.

Stephen is the direct testimonial that the Multilingual Online groups for young men have had a positive end. He arrived in Finland two years ago. He heard of the RAISD project while he was living in a refugee camp. He was at first a final beneficiary, using the forum to get information. Information such as being enrolled in schools, the kind of information, he said, it was not easy to reach out by staying in a camp.

Since last August he is not living in a refugee camp anymore, he works and he is married now. Stephen is currently participating in the Multilingual Online groups for young men, as a moderator and trying to help out other young men that are experiencing the same path he went through.

About the RAISD project, it's very important and actually I saw the essence of it because personally I experienced difficulties when foreigners or immigrants come here and try to integrate, try to get acquainted or adapt to the lifestyle and there are so many problems at your arrival that you go through. As a moderator, I was always motivated because when we were living in the camp it was very difficult. Taking you away from the family or the society and being isolated is very difficult psychologically, so the reason why I decided to be a moderator is basically to help people who are also passing through the same situation and be available for anyone who joined [the forum] and ask questions of what they need. It was a good platform for me to actually use my experience and use what I have learned to give people the advice that they needed especially when they come in, because it is very difficult. It is not an easy thing being at the camp for more than 6 or 7 months. Some people have been there for like 4-5 years, and this affects you psychologically. This is what I want to do, to calm people down whenever they join this forum, give them the necessary information and ask them the things that I know the camp is not going to ask them and support them. So yes, this is me and I am happy to be here.

Figure 2: Stephen Oppong, member of the ARU in Finland

"The Rovaniemi reception centre has been operating for 30 years and the centre has had various activities related to children's activities for several years. It has been interesting to work on an international project"

Ritva Metsälampi is the Director of the Rovaniemi Reception Centre. She has been working in the Centre since December 2015 and has heard about the RAISD project through the Finnish Red Cross Central office, which is one of the stakeholders of the Finnish ARU. The services provided in the reception centre are activities in accordance with the law "Act on the Reception of Applicants for International Protection and the Identification and Assistance of Victims of Trafficking in Human Beings" and the guidelines of the Finnish Immigration Service. The centre provides accommodation for asylum seekers, social work, health care, guidance and counselling, interpreting services, work and study activities, leisure activities and various club activities.

Mrs Ritva has been involved - within the RAISD project - in planning activities in the reception centre collaborating with the University of Helsinki and she has also worked actively in the Finnish network of the project with various actors. During the implementation of the work, there were some difficulties that had caused the fragmentation of the activity plan and less impact than the one expected. "During the project, the reception centre moved to new premises. The premises were not safe in all respects and we had to wait for the renovation work to be completed.

The Covid19 epidemic brought problems to the centre's children's club activities and also to the project's activities for more than a year. When the situation calmed down, there were no more children in the target group at the centre. The parents had obtained a residence permit or had started school and the children had municipal early childhood education."

Mrs Metsälampi continues "We would have liked to have implemented a new operating model for the kids 'club in the project, but unfortunately it did not succeed due to the small number of children. However, we will try to adopt this model later if the number of children of asylum seekers of target age increases. We want to further develop the functions of the centre with asylum seeker families. The implementation of children's club activities is one part of our overall activities."

Among the factors of success, Mrs Metsälampi counts the good experiences interviewing the children's parents and staff. Through the interviews it was possible to learn about the families' wishes for the development of children's hobbies at the reception centre. Also meeting new actors and hearing of different ways of working provided her with new ideas for her own work and for the development of the reception centre.

"We have found that it works, and we want to continue using this strategy"

Raimo Varpula, assistant manager in the Kristiinankaupunki reception centre (Western Finland), and Anneli Turja, a physiotherapist working in the same reception centre, have been involved in developing family services and childcare activities in reception centres.

Figure 3: Representative of the Kristiinankaupunki reception centre (Western Finland)

The reception centre carries on activities from more than 10 years, the centre has been contacted by the Finnish ARU about 3 years ago and since then, they are collaborating in implementing activities focusing on children and involving their parents in each process.

Mr Varpula is in charge of almost everything, managing the office and supporting the staff and the users of the centre. The centre welcomes people coming from several countries, two years ago they had many people coming from Iraq and nowadays the majority are from Russia. Last year the centre was following 20 children and this year 11, and several other children are waiting to access the services the centre is providing. The children currently present at the centre come mostly from Russia, Chechnya, Caucasus region and then also from Middle East, Africa and Nepal. "They come to our centre and they have interviews here and then we find the programme, what is necessary, which professional should follow them" said Mrs Turja.

Mrs Turja works as educator and physiotherapist and with other colleagues she takes care of the children who manifest some delays in motor skills, cognitive skills and also social skills. They work on individual therapy as well as in groups and this is also why they have a limited number of children each year because of the time they have to dedicate to each of them considering that in some cases children also have traumatic backgrounds. "We have three times a week activity connected to work on these skills as they are very important: they are functional for the children's integration, for their wellbeing. This aspect has been managed with success because nine children last year went to the school and the feedback even from the teachers was very positive. Children also knew some Finnish and they possessed important skills before they went to school."

The staff check the improvements in the children using standard tests and the results are wonderful, as told by Mrs Turja. Indeed, one of the major challenges is the parents' involvement in their children's activities and needs. It requires time for the staff to involve them and explain the activities they are following. They often do not receive feedback from the parents during the path, but in the end the parents seem satisfied about the children's improvements. The other challenges to be managed are the different languages and cultural backgrounds that can sometimes slowdown the working process.

7 ARU in Hungary – the work of Menedék

7.1 Background information

Menedék - Hungarian Association for Migrants - promotes social integration of foreign citizens migrating into Hungary, as well as of Hungarian and other citizens emigrating from Hungary. It has a wide network of practitioners and researchers in the field of migration hence it was rather easy to draft a list of possible ARU members with the exception of government actors, due to the attitude of the current government to all issues related with forced migration. In the process of building the ARU, a key conceptual question was whether refugees and stakeholders could work together in meetings that deal with the topic on a higher level of abstraction, not on the level of individual experiences. As an example, it was mentioned that a Post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) patient and a psychologist could work well on a specific traumatic event in the framework of a therapy, but not necessarily in the framework of an ARU meeting. Therefore, ARU was conceived as an essentially stakeholder-focused working group and after that another mechanism was introduced to involve refugees. Another, more practical, issue to be tackled was the language to be used at the meetings. It would have been beneficial to have meetings in English besides (or instead of) Hungarian from the perspective of including foreigners. Yet, it would have had the negative effect of discouraging Hungarian speakers who are not sufficiently fluent in English. Finally, Hungarian was chosen to be the language of the ARU meetings.

Besides the staff members involved in the project management from the start, it was an important principle that different professional skills should be represented, covering the broadest possible range of Menedék's activities. Besides the staff members involved in management, ARU meetings are visited by Menedék's colleagues with considerable expertise in social work, child protection, training and education, legal help and policy analysis. May 2019 was the date of the internal setup of the ARU (within Menedék's team), while the first ARU meeting took place on 16 July 2019.

The ARU has faced different challenges. How were you able to involve different stakeholders of the helix?

NGO and academia were easy to reach. It was difficult to involve representatives of business entities, as well as representatives of central government bodies. We could, however, involve local government representatives and business sector representatives with whom Menedék had ties due to another project about labour market insertion.

How to overcome difficulties in the decision-making process, in the co-creation processes?

Direct involvement of refugees in vulnerability contexts would have been difficult to arrange due to language and availability issues. Instead, the basic topics of RAISD (vulnerability concepts) were introduced to two other groups that are steered by Menedék's social workers, one for immigrant minors and one for immigrant women. Members gave their feedback and it was used in the decision-making process about the TAIS topic and layout. A further ARU meeting was conducted with refugee community leaders during the implementation period of the TAIS.

How to avoid losing the participation of ARU members that are not directly involved in the TAIS? How to motivate stakeholders to participate in the ARUs work?

ARU members have a positive attitude towards 1) Menedék as an organisation, 2) RAISD as a H2020 project. The meetings are seen as a good occasion for structured discussion about important topics. Flow of information was the principal cause for participation, because several service providers work in a setting where information about legal, administrative etc. processes related to BIPs are scarce.

Positive and innovative factors of the ARU working

ARUs recognized that due to resource shortages, social workers at NGOs often use semi-formal channels to help their clients on an individual basis. This practice hinders structural changes and fuels systematic dysfunctions. A clearer vision of competences (both professional and legal) of central and local government institutions, as well as NGOs would help to better address vulnerabilities in a systemic way. These inputs were important for the further steps of the methodological development of TAIS. It is a general phenomenon that different institutions and organizations get involved in the same case, but they do not follow any established methodology or protocol for intervention. Through the discussion with the ARUs, it became evident that rethinking the operational principles of the institutional interventions is necessary. Trained assistants and volunteers can ease HV individuals' access to tailored assistance. As the TAIS profiles showed it, interpersonal ways of assistance can be more efficient and can respond to individuals' long-term needs and enhance better integration.

7.2 A Trajectory monitoring toolbox for tailored intervention

In Hungary, the objective of the TAIS is to enhance refugees' embeddedness in social structures. Social workers and service providers analyse individual cases of vulnerability in order to build a "Trajectory monitoring toolbox" of helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees. ARU members agree that the weakness of refugee integration institutions in Hungary, and the sporadic inter-institutional coordination in the social sphere have a negative effect on the vulnerability of the forcibly displaced: many times, the root of the problem is that a client with complex vulnerabilities does not receive support at the right place, in the right time. Many people fall out of the scope of general supportive services because complex problems cannot be tackled by a service provider alone. While some refugees can rely on an organic supporting environment (family, friends etc) to overcome the traumas and integration difficulties, most of them do not have this background. For the latter group, it is necessary to develop an institutional environment where actors engage in a non-formal, dynamic cooperation based on the organic structures of the host society.

Despite the fact that the Hungarian project partner in RAISD – the Menedék Association – is a key stakeholder in what is related to social work and integration support, in many cases other professional support was needed. In this sense, the ARUs provided insight and showed the way forward in the case of vulnerabilities that could not be tackled with the „tools” of a social worker.

7.3 Testimonials

One particular field of support is related to the trauma and the coping mechanisms that were built around it. One ARU member, Lilla Hárdi has the medical and psychiatric expertise working with patients with post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). She has been involved in the mental care and healing of those experiencing war trauma. Working as a council and executive committee member of the Copenhagen-based International Rehabilitation and Research Council for Torture Victims, she dealt with abuses in collaboration with UNHCR - her patients were mainly refugees or asylum seekers. In 1996, she was one of the founders of the Cordelia Foundation, which was established to rehabilitate tortured and abused asylum seekers and refugees and provide mental-health assistance. She is a member of the IRCT (International Rehabilitation Council for Torture Victims) and received the Inge Genefke Prize in 2014, awarded to those who help victims. Lilla Hárdi has been interviewed about the situation about the intervention on the refugees topic in Hungary and the work of the TAIS implemented by the Hungarian ARU.

Figure 4: Lilla Hárdi, member of the ARU in Hungary

Menedék: From your perspective, how does the network of institutions, organizations and specific areas seem to provide help for vulnerable refugees in Hungary?

Lilla Hárdi: There are two systems in Hungary – the state system and the NGO system working independently. Although the NGOs used to strive to cooperate with the public sphere, in the last decade this intention was fluctuating, as well as the reaction to it from the public sphere. The state system works on the surface level, where only a superficial caretaking is provided. A typical example can be food supplies, which are provided to those in need so that authorities can “tick a box”, but these supplies are not adequate for the modern dietary needs. This is the setting in which the NGOs try to cooperate in order to assist one individual or a group.

In your work is it the formal or informal channel of assistance that works better?

In the non-governmental areas the individual is of utmost importance, we do not pass around our clients from place to place but we try to help them to the best of our abilities, even though we often run into dead end streets in the maze of the system. If the communication is inadequate, it is the client who suffers.

How can the cooperation in the ARU meetings between psychiatric, social and legal assistance be fruitful?

Cooperation can work with daily dialogues and common discussion forums. In Hungary there is a considerable network of civil society organizations, forming for more than 20 years, but it requires forums like the ARU meetings to maintain these ties. We have developed a resilient network that surrounds the individual in need of assistance, and we are supporting and pushing them through the maze of the system.

Would the material which is currently prepared in the TAIS pilot be useful or adoptable for someone working in your practice?

In my opinion it is useful and we are already using it, we adapt or follow many practices. Team meetings and the constant information sharing around an individual is extremely important, as are the meetings of a larger platform, clear instructions from management, keeping the feedback system open and, most importantly, maintaining constant contact and trust.

A key output of the TAIS in Hungary is a training material developed for social workers which will contain typical vulnerable profiles, and a toolkit to aid self-reflection which can be used by social workers in their daily work, helping them to review their relationship with a client and the preconceptions in their work. Could you imagine something similar to be used or adapted to your profession?

I can absolutely see that happening. Although the main focus of our work is the vulnerable client, if someone has any difficulties in regard to this there is – or there was – the opportunity of supervision, which provides space to talk about these issues, to psychologically process them. Now, in the online world, it has become slightly difficult.

There are 9 months left in the project, what would be a useful topic for discussion in the upcoming ARU meetings?

I believe we could discuss the changes in the world that have happened since the pandemic started. Another idea is to share experiences about the fluctuating clientele in this area, and what kind of new issues are coming to the surface.

“A dynamic and easy-to-use guideline that social workers can follow when they are working with forcibly displaced people with different vulnerability profiles”

Other members have added further layers of understanding to the ARU's approach. One member has had the expertise about asylum law, with a focus on Dublin III procedures that are of relevance in Hungary. Another key ARU member is an expert in the field of social service provider institutions and welfare allowances, crisis lodging, and institutional protection of victims of domestic violence, while yet another recurring member of the ARU meetings has the experience in developing and managing a wide range of national and international projects implemented by international organizations, charity and relief agencies. Knowing the structures within which specific vulnerabilities are dealt with is also of utmost importance. Based on inputs like these, the ARU could develop multi-faceted response strategies for different vulnerability contexts. Trajectories of real (anonymized) people in real-life situations is now leading to the publication of a dynamic and easy-to-use guideline that social workers can follow when they are working with forcibly displaced people with different vulnerability profiles. This will be one of the key takeaways of the TAIS in Hungary.

Figure 5: Working on the self-reflection methodology for vulnerable clients

8 ARU in Turkey – the work of Anadolu University

8.1 Background information

The ARU in Turkey is managed by Anadolu University located in Eskişehir. In order to build the Research Unit, Anadolu University relied on active relations with various stakeholders from the local community. These stakeholders include civil society organisations, special and specific centres, local government-municipalities, bar association, private sector, chamber of commerce and industrial field establishments, media, education sector, research and others. At the same time, besides the institutional relations, the ARU also built upon individual relations established through various projects and events. Right at the beginning of the RAISD project, the Anadolu University team started establishing semi-formal talks and exchanges about establishing the ARU team, which would hold the members of those stakeholders. Moreover, these actors (particularly centres and civil society organizations) were able to suggest other potential members and most importantly to involve FDPs directly into the ARU team. Simply, the Anadolu University team followed these suggestions. The main contribution was from WGSS-Women and Girls Safe Spaces centre. Through those centres, the Anadolu University team established and continued strong relations with FDPs on behalf of the ARU and necessary for the ARU work. The COVID-19 outbreak and the particularly growing tension and conflicts in the country (also connected to the hate in public towards FDPs), have produced an unfortunate constant change in the members of the Turkish ARU. But, their commitment in ARU and TAIS work was very effective despite the difficulties.

The Anadolu University team guided the process of TAIS definition and design, with a strong commitment and involvement in the TAIS implementation and training on behalf of the ARU members. All in all, 16 members joined the Action Research Unit, including representatives of the business and industry, policy-makers, researchers and FDP. The aim of the TAIS in Turkey is to create capacities, awareness and understanding for various stakeholders in terms of inclusion and diversity – overall for integration – for forcibly displaced people. Through the workshops on understanding the concepts of diversity and inclusion, and the way monitoring functions, vulnerable populations - forcibly displaced people are the main beneficiaries while society in general through various stakeholders is the beneficiary for a better integrated society.

8.2 Diversity and inclusion, monitoring and advocacy

The Turkish ARU, in its work towards the inclusion of FDP, has set three levels of expected results. First, to develop an understanding on diversity and inclusion concepts for all participating sides. Second, to understand the role of monitoring and use it as a tool for advocacy. Third, to put monitoring into action and utilize it in a systematic way. For their contribution to the ARU stories, the ARU members and TAIS target audience produced the following text. All indicated that they would prefer not to produce the video and/or being on records. Therefore, their experience has been narrated as below.

“Diversity training, inclusion training and monitoring training”

As defined in the descriptions, particularly for the TAIS, Anadolu University team worked with ARU members that are NOT project members and also directly the target audience of TAIS. Accordingly, all the team members wanted to see if we could come up with something innovative and something new that has never been done before and would

also have a unique solution for the core of the project. During the series of ARU meetings, it was realized by ARU members and particularly by FDP members, that the "service" area was the crucial one on which to direct attention and efforts. There was a significant dimension in the service providers that ARU members and FDPs underlined the importance of developing capacities that in return would help their lives. Long discussions and questions helped all members to understand and realize that "local authorities" (municipalities in Turkey, particularly in the city of Eskisehir) were lacking in services in terms of their qualities. Then, discussions were directed towards the local government and all members understood that service providers (particularly to FDPs) in local government (municipality of Eskisehir- 'Greater Municipality of Eskisehir') did never take any training on sensitivities and awareness towards FDPs and other related communities.

Series of discussions with ARU members, target audience of TAIS- municipality service providers and participants of city council, local government and others as a result underlined the importance of 'rights-based approaches', 'needs based approaches', 'community-based approaches', and 'value-based approaches' as behalf of the foreseen trainings. All teams agreed on training. FDPs and local government members were in full agreement and they defined the great need for those trainings so they would totally benefit service providers and beneficiaries of those services - which they were FDPs.

Discussions between groups came to the final conclusion, in which all members agreed to conduct a series of trainings, which are 'diversity training', 'inclusion training' and 'monitoring training'. Local government members, as defined, had never had those trainings. Particularly, all members underlined the importance of diversity and inclusion trainings. Later, they also indicated that monitoring training would be also essential because it would bring a kind of follow up and would give elements to understand the qualities of services produced. Meanwhile, all members also underlined that 'monitoring' would also serve as an 'advocacy tool' for the service providers in terms of policy development and other related reasons, because they would accumulate a significant amount of experience. Then, the local government realised another need. They shared that it would be great to have a basic and easy to follow 'monitoring tool' for their services so they can be more aware of the principles of their work that can produce meaning and value for FDPs in their services.

All decisions were made with open discussions and with full agreements. ARU members, uniquely FDPs and target audiences (local government) produced the outcomes. They defined the needs, so it can be said that no decision and conclusion was given but defined by the groups in need. In the end, everyone, particularly FDPs and local government as service providers to FDPs, were very happy that it will bring something new and first time to do for the lives of vulnerable people and FDPs. Local government members happily indicated that this means a new dimension for service quality and capacity for the employees. FDP members indicated that it would produce qualified services for their needs in short and mid-term, and also create new policies for their well-being long-term.

9 ARU in Jordan – the work of Yarmouk University

9.1 Background information

The Jordanian ARU is led by Yarmouk University. The process of setting up the ARU started with the involvement of the Refugees, displaced persons and forced migration studies centre (RDBFMSC) at Yarmouk University and the NAWAFTH organization for training and sustainable development in Irbid. The two institutions helped to gather and communicate with several other Jordanian stakeholders (NGOs, community leaders, associations, government organization, academic institutions) and to reach refugees, immigrants and displaced people in Jordan. The team of the ARU is wide and distributed over Jordanian regions (North, Middle, and South) which is indeed an added value for the work of the Unit, but on the other hand it was a big challenge to find an appropriate date and time to invite them to Yarmouk University (YU), worsened by the spread of the COVID-19 in the country. The ARU is well connected with staff and members at the University, it was received positively and fit in the overall mission of the institution. The ARU is fully operational from September 2019, the first meetings with refugees were held in January 2020. Since all ARU members are highly qualified and experienced persons, their inputs have been very valuable for the project, for the definition of the vulnerability context and the design of the TAIS. Main task was indeed to get from them the highest amount of information possible.

The ARU in Jordan designed a TAIS focused on psychosocial support for refugees. The Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF) aims to provide a structure that contributes to the well-being of individuals and prevents the need for medical support through non-clinical interventions. It aims at breaking barriers and creating connections, promoting awareness and understanding of the importance of psychosocial support (PSS) and sharing knowledge on approaches, research, practice, and policy that impact on the provision of support to vulnerable forcibly displaced people. The TAIS in Jordan aims at implementing psychosocial support through economic empowerment and promoting financial knowledge. Health awareness, legal awareness and psychological well-being are also key elements in the support mechanism.

9.2 A multi-disciplinary approach towards psychological well-being

According to many refugee interviews, the support provided in reception centres or by NGOs is neither sufficient nor efficient, due to the constant change of trainers and the diversity of educational backgrounds of the refugees. On the other hand, COVID-19 has had a significant impact on the psychosocial well-being of vulnerable refugees in Jordan. Negative factors include exposure to violence, stress accumulation, loss of family members or separation from family members, deteriorating living conditions, inability to support oneself and family, increased militarization and divisions in communities, and lack of access to services. These can all have immediate consequences, as well as long-term consequences, for the displaced. Indeed, the ARU in Jordan relied on experts from many different fields, to grant a wide-ranging perspective to the Unit. The multi-disciplinary approach is performed with inputs gathered from the legal perspective, child protection, business services providers, medical and health experts, psychological support and psychological treatment perspective, capacity building, training and sustainable development. The rationale is to develop a Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF) which covers distinct modules and combines interactive training methods, in-house seminars, e-learning and field activities or short-term internships. Feedback

sessions and training evaluations are used to increasingly fine-tune the contents and set-up of the training material in order to better equip psychosocial support service providers, over time.

The ARU has faced different challenges. How were you able to involve different stakeholders of the helix? How to overcome difficulties in the decision-making process, in the co-creation processes?

The ARU aimed at involving stakeholders to fully represent the helix, but several challenges arose. It took a long time to get approval from many stakeholders to participate, because they have long and bureaucratic internal procedures. Then, the participants were not assigned by us but the organisations themselves, with the results of having in the ARU some members with little expertise in the issue. In this sense, the support of the local NGO (NAWAFTH) and the Refugee study centre was essential to engage the key people for the job. Another challenge was that the organization participants were so cautious with providing data since their organizations do not allow them to share information and policies and strategies. Last, there was a need to translate questions into Arabic to make the discussion clear and understandable, especially because a large group could not speak or understand English, such as some of the participants and refugee students.

How to avoid losing the participation of ARU members that are not directly involved in the TAIS? How to motivate stakeholders to participate in the ARUs work?

There is a structural peculiarity of the ARU, i.e. most participants come from the local partners or as persons who volunteer in the project, so that we hope to promote integration between all members as NGOs and individuals, which will in turn grant to everyone to be fully heard, actively participate and remain in contact over the long-run.

9.3 Testimonials

“The training helped me to grow personally and professionally”

The first testimonial from Jordan is Limar Qtaifan, a Syrian refugee involved in the training program promoted by the ARU on Psychological Support for Refugees. She opens her testimony highlighting the great sufferance due to psychological distress during the COVID-19 pandemic. The delivery of the training online did not help, since it was an unfamiliar and complex way of learning, with unstable connection and many distractions. When participants went back in class, other challenges arose: difficulties in reaching the classroom due to problems in transportation, plus only limited students could actually attend due to the social distancing restrictions. Despite all that, the course was successful and useful. Limar stated that she acquired many skills that contributed to her personal development, improved thinking abilities and engaged her in dynamic activities, reducing the stress and pressure imposed by the pandemic. In addition, she learned much about the refugees' rights in Jordan, from a legal, health and family perspective. Most importantly, the training program helped enhancing self-confidence, making connections with friends and colleagues and having a positive impact on participants, contributing to professional development and social integration.

The testimony is available here: <https://youtu.be/2K-7m7xclal>

“I am now self-independent and more able to secure my living expenses”

Muhammad Al-Heissa is the second Syrian refugee interviewed for the ARU Stories. He took part in a training on Economic and Legal empowerment, which was really relevant for him. He learned he was in the condition of starting his own business, while before, as a Syrian refugee, he was not aware of such a possibility. The greatest achievement was relying on himself and securing a living for his family. Moreover, the training was also the occasion to get familiar with online learning and digital tools. All in all, the support offered by the ARU helped both professionally and personally, providing trainees with skills and a valuable life-experience, reducing the feeling of shame which is often connected with the need for psychological support. The testimony is available here: https://youtu.be/i5Dts_4OWvQ

Figure 6: Muhammad Al-Heissa is a Syrian refugee interviewed for the ARU Stories

“We used to connect, meet and share our experiences”

The third testimonial for the Jordanian ARU is Kefaya Khader. She reported her experience as part of the RAISD research team. She was indeed included in the ARU due to the wide expertise in community social support and refugees’ organisations, with the scope of providing services to the largest number of refugees in Jordan. The value of being part of the ARU lied in the opportunity to connect, meet and share experiences. Moreover, it provided us with a new perspective: helping those in real need, with a more tailored approach, to help them find the right service, the right place, the right path, upon their specific needs and specific interests. The positive impact of the project will stay as a long-term result for her, and for all the practitioners and organizations working with refugees.

The testimony is available here: <https://youtu.be/X8-t87lWDGE>

10 ARU in Lebanon – the work of the Lebanese International University (LIU)

10.1 Background information

The Lebanese ARU was built as a working group in the framework of the university's Centre of Excellence for Research and Development. The Centre vision is to promote faculty and student research and the University's research culture by increasing the visibility and the recognition of faculty and students, and by fostering an environment conducive to research and the creation of knowledge. In this sense, the work of the Centre was very instrumental to the establishment of the ARU, which became a tassel in the overall strategy of the university to increase the impact of research, strengthen and support interdisciplinarity and significantly improve the wide-range of services offered. With LIU dispersed in 9 geographic areas in Lebanon, it was easy for the university to get a wide and high number of stakeholders involved in the ARU establishment and working routine. The ARU members selected have strong relationships with the civil society and with their geographic area in the country. A key conceptual decision was the inception of key stakeholders who work directly with refugees, building on the work conducted in previous projects (i.e. RESCUE project and the R-SOS units).

Indeed, the Lebanese TAIS focuses on Syrian students living in refugee camps and those who are underprivileged to enrol in school, along with Syrians who will be fully empowered to develop skills and minimize educational impediments. Inclusion of Syrian refugees is a constant challenge in the country and the TAIS aims to contribute to addressing the issue. Due to the pandemic outbreak in the country, preceded and followed by other crises in Lebanon over the course of the project implementation, the focus of the TAIS shifted towards Health literacy and awareness. The Lebanese TAIS has been shaped by the necessities emerging from the COVID-19 pandemic, most importantly among Syrian refugees living in Lebanon. The TAIS aims to provide a series of trainings and instruction about health awareness, but also to explore how participation in health awareness work affects vulnerable people's motivation and identity, and what is the right role for trainers to raise this awareness. It looks for explanations about how vulnerable respond to an online awareness campaign to health issues, and how training can use a mix of media and technology in order to fit vulnerable people's needs.

10.2 Excellence and inclusion as driving forces of the Lebanese ARU

The potential of the Lebanese ARU lies in the involvement of different actors, from the project focal point to the university governance (represented by the Provost and the Vice-President who joined several meetings), researchers, civil society representatives and supportive colleagues from the Excellence Centre. It was a founding principle that different professional skills should be represented, involving colleagues working in management, colleagues with a considerable expertise in social work, child protection, training and education, legal help and policy analysis. With the COVID-19 outbreak, and to cope with the difficulties generated by the pandemic, a staff member from the LIU Health Committee was also involved, so as to work in tandem with the objectives of the ARU. As a result, policy-makers, researchers, experts and strategic institutional figures were engaged in the ARU working, building on the principles of excellence and inclusion. More stakeholders were in the plan, but due to a number of unforeseen risk factors, their direct involvement was not possible; instead, they were consulted as interviewees for the definition of the vulnerability context and the TAIS. Most of the challenges faced by LIU were related to the political unrest that hit the country from October 2019 till Mid December of 2019. As a consequence, participants were so cautious with

discussing and providing data, and traveling around the country was impeded with road blocks. Despite that, in December 2019 the ARU was set up, and the first ARU meeting took place in January 2020, followed by other meetings along the year for a total of 4 encounters. The big picture of the ARU strategy was clear from the start, yet it was only in January that a well-defined micro-operation started to click and the basic topics of RAISD were introduced to the group. Meetings were held in February and subsequently virtual contacts were scheduled to move forward with the TAIS implementation and in general to keep the ARU alive, up and running.

The ARU has faced different challenges. How were you able to involve different stakeholders of the helix?

LIU started by clarifying clearly the objectives of stakeholder engagement, embedding their participation in a framework of research use. Therefore, they have been involved in the research phase and in the definition of the vulnerability context, in the adaptation of the TAIS to the current health challenges in the country (for example by actively involving the newly established HHealth COmmittee), in the definition of recommendations. They all knew they had the potential to play a key role and were committed to do so.

How to overcome difficulties in the decision-making process, in the co-creation processes?

We co-created a Journey Map to follow up on the ARU members recommendations and suggestions, to enhance research and the development of the project.

How to avoid losing the participation of ARU members that are not directly involved in the TAIS? How to motivate stakeholders to participate in the ARUs work?

Because one of our ARU members is a former Minister, we held regular informational and educational meetings. His influence helped offer the attendees a chance to voice their concerns and/or to share their ideas at the meetings. He incorporated a motivational tone and message into the meetings that got the stakeholders excited. . He has a very good motive to activate potential members, and sustain their positions.

Positive and innovative factors of the ARU working

The LIU Health Committee worked to enrich all stakeholders with the coping tools needed to enhance them in developing their awareness and minimize the challenges in facing the COVID 19 pandemic trauma. As per the discussions that took place during the ARU meetings, vulnerable groups among forcibly displaced Syrian refugees have problems accessing to:

- Basic health services
- Education services
- Application mechanisms for necessary issues

According to the ARU and Advisory Board members, elderly, maternal women and young infants age 6 are the riskiest group among vulnerable groups. Therefore, all mentioned accessing basic health services is one of the most important issues for such vulnerable groups. Many refugees in Lebanon do not have access to free healthcare services, as they do not have legal refugee status. In parallel with access to health services, the problem of accessing information mechanisms also arises. Especially due to the COVID-19 outbreak, PCR testing became a stumbling issue

to such groups taking into account the cost. In addition, the lack of beds, protection and isolation facilities to contain contagion, the risk of getting the virus was high enough.

According to ARU and Advisory Board members, another important issue is access to education. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, an online committee regarding teaching was requested to be formed and a website to deliver online training was established around mid-March 2020. In addition, those who had access to TV broadcasts and/or internet, could get some guidelines with all videos developed in Arabic as many have language barriers.

“Direct our trained students to move to their camps and to disseminate the information they have acquired, in order to raise the health awareness of the Syrian refugees in the Bekaa region”

The story of the Lebanese ARU is narrated by different voices. First, we hear the feedback of the Chair of the LIU Health Committee, Dr. Ahmad Faraj, on the intervention and support provided by the Health Committee to vulnerable communities through the RAISD project. The entering of the HC in the project was functional to the reaching of the ARU's goals and support for refugee students. In fact, the HC was able to identify a number of Syrian refugee students, assess their skills on several matters and provide them with a series of training workshops. The training focused on health literacy, mobile-media use, communication and leadership skills and digital literacy, as it was reported by the second voice in the video, that of the student Nour Darwich. The training was performed online and addressed to the Syrian refugee students located in the Bekaa region, where the refugee camp is. It was rich in information and useful, in the words of Mohammad Al-Abar, another student who benefited from the work done at LIU by the Lebanese ARU. The HC aims for these students to transfer the knowledge acquired through the people staying at the refugee camp, so to raise their awareness on health matters, vaccination and much more.

The testimony is available here: <https://youtu.be/EGUcHuND2-Q>

11 Conclusions

The ARUs Research stories document aims at tracing the working methodology, the innovative elements, the criticalities and the achievements of the ARUs implemented by the RAISD project. In fact, the value of this exercise lies in the collection of different inputs from a wide range of stakeholders, including the project partners who acted as ARU leaders and, as such, the drivers of the TAIS implementations.

The ARUs and their outputs - the TAIS - represent a very wide and diversified range of contexts and actors, from a Nordic country such as Finland to Middle East countries - such as Lebanon and Jordan, going through Hungary, Turkey, Spain and Italy, and experiencing profoundly different impacts of the migration phenomenon. In particular, it is noteworthy that in Lebanon and Jordan the percentage of refugees in the broadest sense is considered to be equal to 35% of the total population, thus generating a high pressure on the local society and on the availability of resources and services. Also, in Turkey the pressure is very high, whereas none of the involved EU countries experiences similar levels of presence, but the issue of accepting and integrating different types of migrants is still very relevant in the political agendas of these countries.

Considering these relevant aspects, it is quite impossible to formulate a unique and homogeneous statement about the weaknesses and strengths of the implementation of ARUs and TAIS in the participating countries, however in this section we try to elicit common elements and considerations.

The involvement of Stakeholders

Involving a wide range of stakeholders to implement the quintuple helix approach was one of the driving factors in the implementation of the ARUs and it turned out to be one of the key issues in terms of implementing the ARUs. By definition, not all the members of the ARUs are partners of the project, therefore their participation must happen on a voluntary basis and respond to a different type of motivation. Motivating the participation of external stakeholders, not only at the stage of setting up of the ARU, but also, and more importantly in the implementation of the TAIS, i.e. convincing them not to leave the ARU, appears to be one of the major challenges and therefore a lesson learnt in the whole project. Hence, in terms of sustainability and potential replication of the experience, the forms of return and benefits for the participants should be the subject of a deep reflection e.g. in terms of image, training, capacity building, networking and so on. For instance, in terms of training, a whole set of training courses for ARU members at large, on transversal topics such as participatory approach, RRI, gender issues, psychological support and trauma management and the like was organised, delivered, recorded and uploaded to the UNIMED's eLearning platform and to the project website. This is an example of useful return for the participating stakeholders which is deemed to motivate them.

Moreover, the Partners had to cope with the limitations and restrictions related to the COVID-19 pandemic, which prevented face-to-face meetings and developing real connections between members. Smart ways to reduce the impact of the pandemic were found, starting from the use of digital tools towards more participatory approaches.

Indeed, each ARU found its strategy and way to keep the stakeholders interested and motivated and involved in its work. Among the different cases we can mention the following examples: definition of clear and long-term cooperation objectives, setting up a common quality framework, joint monitoring of critical points of the

implementation cycles and even the involvement of a former Minister participating in the meetings to guarantee the other members to have their voices heard at institutional level. Other ways of engaging stakeholders included always keeping them updated and continuously designing beneficial things, being reliable and showing competence on the subject, and then creating occasions for sharing and discussing information on the matter, creating synergies and integration among the actors participating in the ARU to provide long term collaborations.

The involvement of final beneficiaries

How to motivate and attract the final beneficiaries of the TAIS and keep them engaged over time? Once excluded the possibility of providing financial support, each ARU was left free to operate in the way they thought to be more effective. The return for the beneficiaries was clearer in terms of training services they received through the project, or providing direct testimonials within the implementation of the ARU (such as the Spanish ARU participation in the RAISD documentary). One of the outstanding results of the pilots in fact was that the participants very much appreciated the possibility of expressing themselves and their needs in a fully participatory approach, following the principles of RRI (mainly through the involvement of a wide range of stakeholders in a fully deployed quintuple Helix approach). Being an active part of the processes put in place by the ARU (starting from the definition of the vulnerability contexts towards being involved in the design and piloting of the TAIS) engaged final beneficiaries in an innovative way, transforming them from passive actors into co-creators of the project steps, outcomes and achievements. It allowed many beneficiaries, both direct and indirect, to create new personal and professional connections, reduce isolation and support their ideas, projects and full integration in the social context.

The impact of the COVID 19 pandemic

The outbreak of the COVID 19 pandemic was obviously not foreseen at the time of writing the proposal, it was not included in the risk analysis and mitigation plan, and was an unexpected challenge for the project Partners. Almost the totality of European-funded projects was highly impacted by the pandemic, especially due to long lockdown periods and the impossibility of traveling, and most of them had to restructure their work plans, timings and project duration. This was also the case of RAISD project, which asked for a time extension, to adjust the program and action plan to the new context and avoid delays (especially in the implementation of the TAIS) due to the COVID-19 restrictions and also, to give stakeholders time to readjust and recover from the social and psychological consequences of a worldwide health crisis.

Looking specifically at the impact of the pandemic on the pilots, if we want to find the silver lining, the positive aspect was that it forced the ARU members to find, as far as possible, alternative solutions for carrying out the pilots. Of course, not all the activities which were designed to be carried out in presence could be turned into online activities, therefore forcing the ARU members to modify their ways of working, to invent new solutions to the problem and to develop the capacity of adaptation, these aspects being at the very core of the RRI principles of adaptative change and flexibility. On the other hand, it also strengthened the digital competences and digital literacy of beneficiaries, who were obliged to follow activities online. This was challenging, especially if we think about vulnerable groups with difficulties in accessing PCs and internet connections. However, in an always more digital global world, it provided them with new crucial and essential skills to manage their future. This is clearly another positive effect of the project.

The achievements of the ARU

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Del. 7.1 Research stories from ARUs: report and analysis [October, 2021]

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Action Research Units were born as one of the innovative elements of the RAISD project. Over the past 3 years, they became the milestones upon which the TAIS were imagined, piloted and enriched to cope with unexpected challenges. ARU have shown their great potential, their capacity to influence the context, to drive the change, and generate a positive impact on the lives of the beneficiaries, the vulnerable groups. They have adapted, they have suffered, they have committed to the set goals. Time will say if these achievements stay over time, keep producing life-changing outcomes and involve relevant stakeholders. As far as we heard in the ARU stories, all ARUs seem to be on the right track to successfully move forward and concrete plans are made for the future sustainability for the ARUs.

A decorative banner with a background of overlapping, colorful triangles in shades of purple, blue, green, yellow, and orange.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 822688.

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